

The BioWhere Gazetteer: A Culturally Enriched Place Name Knowledge Base for New Zealand

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Abstract:

Gazetteers link place names to their geographic footprints and associated contextual knowledge. While traditionally used in cartography and geography, modern gazetteers have evolved into extensive sources of geographic intelligence. However, within Aotearoa New Zealand's rich cultural and historical landscape, existing gazetteers often lack the capacity to integrate conventional geographic datasets with indigenous, narrative-rich place name resources. We propose a culturally enriched gazetteer model for Aotearoa New Zealand, extending the Alexandria Digital Library (ADL) Gazetteer Content Standard (GCS) to integrate geospatial and cultural dimensions. The proposed model consolidates data from authoritative datasets such as the Land Information New Zealand (LINZ) gazetteer and volunteered geographic information (VGI) platforms like GeoNames and OpenStreetMap. A key innovation is the inclusion of Māori cultural knowledge through *whakapapa*, the lineage, stories, and histories associated with place names, enabled by extending the etymology component of the ADL model. Structured as a relational database, the gazetteer supports multiple names, feature types, and geometries per place, while maintaining temporal information and source provenance. It accommodates bilingual names in Māori and English, as well as alternative spellings, abbreviations, and variants, reflecting the linguistic diversity of New Zealand's toponymy. Another distinctive feature of this gazetteer is the integration of georeferenced locality descriptions derived from biodiversity collection records. These often refer to unnamed or informally described places, and their inclusion facilitates georeferencing tasks by centralising both named and descriptive spatial data. The database is populated via an Extract, Transform, Load (ETL) pipeline in PostgreSQL, using PostGIS for spatial data maintenance. We also plan to incorporate self-learning capabilities to infer coordinates for previously unrecorded place names. Upon completion, this gazetteer aims to serve as a repository of New Zealand's geographic features and cultural heritage, encompassing more locations than existing gazetteers for the region, and supporting GIS, ecology, digital humanities, and indigenous knowledge systems.

Keywords: Digital Gazetteer, GIS Integration, Māori Place Names

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